

Squamous Cell Carcinoma Skin Cancer: The Increasing Demand for Artificial Intelligence Driven Diagnosis in Africa

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Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC) is one of the most prevalent and deadliest skin cancers considered a major cause of mortality worldwide. Artificial Intelligence driven diagnosis can assist clinicians in achieving much more accurate and precise diagnosis with lesser effort thereby improving survival chances of patients. Thus, this study presents the use of Artificial Intelligence for SCC diagnosis and emphasizes the need for widespread adoption, especially in Africa with the aim of improving the healthcare system within the continent. A systematic review highlighting the trends in Artificial Intelligence diagnostic models for skin cancer diagnosis was conducted and reported. Several studies have been carried out on the use of Artificial Intelligence for skin cancer diagnosis. Results reveal a great potential of AI to significantly reduce the mortality rate of skin cancer related diseases through accurate and timely diagnosis of skin cancer in Africa. At present, empirical findings reveal certain barriers and limitations for widespread adoption of computer-aided techniques in Africa including availability of benchmark datasets, willingness of adoption, awareness of the technology by clinical practitioners. These barriers and limitations pose a major threat to accurate and timely diagnosis, and effective treatment of SCC in Africa.

Keywords
Artificial Intelligence, Skin Cancer, Convolutional Neural Networks, Clinical Diagnosis

Introduction

The skin protects the underlying body from external environmental factors such as temperature variations, ultraviolet radiation, chemicals, and other related threats (Kumar *et al.*, 2019). Skin cancer is a worldwide threat, and the major skin cancers include basal cell carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and melanoma. Squamous cell carcinoma is the second most cutaneous malignancy after Basal Cell Carcinoma (BCC) with a global hike in the number of cases (Barsouk *et al.*, 2023; Peris *et al.*, 2019; Warszawik-Hendzel *et al.*, 2015). Africa with its current struggle with poor healthcare has a high prevalence of Squamous Cell Carcinoma (Effiom *et al.*, 2008; Onuigbo & Njeze, 2016; Wu *et al.*, 2023). SCC is one of the deadliest forms of skin cancer, accounting for approximately 82% of skin cancer-related deaths in Africa. Notwithstanding the harmful nature of this disease, if diagnosed in a timely and accurate manner, the chances of survival of affected individuals remain high (Sagar & Dheeba, 2020). This can be seen as the most effective way to increase the survival rate of

patients with SCC. The development and use of Dermoscopy techniques can significantly facilitate the accuracy of early detection of skin cancers (Brinker *et al.*, 2018; Khan *et al.*, 2020). Clinically, several heuristic techniques based on Dermoscopy rules such as “ABCD” rule (Cognetta *et al.*, 1994), and “CASH” (Henning *et al.*, 2007) have been used for diagnosis of skin cancers. Manual diagnosis of squamous cell carcinoma is a non-trivial process, and because of the complexity of biopsy as a traditional approach to clinical diagnosis, mistakes can occur leading to several complications, inaccurate diagnosis and delays which can significantly affect the survival chances of patients with SCC. Dermoscopy technology, a non-invasive skin imaging technique that uses polarized light to make the contact area translucent and can reveal the sub-surface skin structure, and is widely adopted in developed countries to improve the diagnostic accuracy of skin cancers (A.-R. Ali *et al.*, 2020). Manual examination of these Dermoscopy images using some of the aforementioned Dermoscopy

examination techniques is not only time consuming, experimental and error prone, but also subject to the expertise of the dermatologist carrying out the diagnosis (Tajeddin & Asl, 2018; Xu *et al.*, 2020). Consequently, computer-aided solutions have been introduced by the computer-oriented research community using Artificial Intelligence (AI) to assist dermatologists in automatically diagnosing this disease at its early stages so that appropriate and timely treatment can be commenced (Celebi *et al.*, 2007; Barata *et al.*, 2014; Farooq *et al.*, 2016; Azzahidi *et al.*, 2020). Machine learning and image processing in medical applications help physicians and radiologists reduce the complexity of the problem and facilitate speedy detection and treatment of cancer. Some machine learning techniques proposed to assist clinicians in medical diagnosis include Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), and Neural Network Ensembles (Yang *et al.*, 2018). However, because the extracted features are somewhat low-level and handcrafted in a traditional machine learning setting, these traditional classification methods are less robust for solving complex skin lesion issues.

Compared to Neural Networks that were used before 2012, Deep Learning (DL) models have been widely adopted for image analysis processes. More specifically, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) which consist of convolutional filters capable of detecting low-level structures such as colors, contrasts, and edges. Following this, researchers have adopted deep learning techniques (Greenspan *et al.*, 2016), especially CNNs which have shown tremendous performance and powerful generalization ability in the task of medical imaging analysis. This can also be attributed to the increased amount of data and the recent availability of high computational power. Deep learning can learn multiple levels of representation from raw image data, and the extracted features are high-

level and robust (Mathew *et al.*, 2021). Although the method is complicated, deep learning algorithms have shown exceptional performance in visual tasks and even outperformed humans in gaming and object recognition, as seen in the ImageNet Large Scale Recognition Challenge (ILSRC) from 2010 to 2016, which has led to several studies on the automated screening of skin cancers. In the light of this, several studies have been conducted to leverage the advantages of deep learning in computer-aided diagnosis of skin cancer (Hekler *et al.*, 2019; Sreelatha *et al.*, 2019). Although there is a relatively lower prevalence of SCC in Africa than in Europe and other continents (Yakubu & Mabogunje, 1995; Samaila & Adesiyun, 2006; Oseni *et al.*, 2015; Oo *et al.*, 2019; Salawu *et al.*, 2022), affected individuals in Africa are more likely to die from this disease because of the relatively poor healthcare system. Therefore, it is important to develop, implement, and deploy computer-aided platforms to assist clinicians in effectively diagnosing SCC accurately and in a time manner. This study aims to explore the current state of AI-driven diagnostic techniques for SCC in Africa, identify barriers to their adoption, and propose pathways for their effective implementation.

Prevalence of SCC in Africa

Africa is the world's second largest and second most populous continent after Asia. At approximately 30.3 million km² inclusive of adjacent islands, it covers 20% of the earth's land area and 6% of its total surface area. Africa is bounded by the Mediterranean Sea, Red Sea, Indian Ocean, and Atlantic Ocean. With a population of nearly 1.4 billion, it accounts for 18% of the world's human population. There has been a series of reports on SCC incidence in different parts of Africa. In sub-Saharan Africa (Faggons *et al.*, 2015). Examination of 8611 patients reveal 410 patients (4.8%) of all cases were diagnosed with SCC of the Nasopharynx, 385 patients (4.5%) were diagnosed with Laryngeal SCC,

and 66 patients (0.8%) were diagnosed with hypopharyngeal SCC. In South Africa, (Kgomo *et al.*, 2017) reported an examination of 6118 patients in which 59 patients aged 27 to 87 years, were diagnosed with SCC giving a prevalence of 0.96%, 95% confidence interval. (Ohayi, 2022) reported the sampling of 695 skin lesions from 540 albino patients (275 males, 241 females, and 24 anonymous gender). 491 cases of SCC were identified resulting in a prevalence of 64% and 95% confidence intervals. In Addis Ababa, Ethiopia (Yosef *et al.*, 2024) examined 15,075 patients of whom 3.8% (570) were histopathologically diagnosed with SCC. 50.3% patients were female, and nearly 70% were reported after >1 year of symptom onset.

Artificial Intelligence (Convolutional Neural Networks)

The increase in the amount of text, images, and videos available in data repositories and on the Web has increased the demand for deep learning technology in a variety of applications. In visual recognition, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are the most widely adopted and established algorithms among the deep learning algorithms after performing best in the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) (Russakovsky *et al.*, 2015). In medical research, CNNs have also shown tremendous performance in clinical diagnosis in areas such as diabetic retinopathy screening, lymph node metastasis detection, and skin cancer diagnosis which has led to an increasing interest in CNN especially among radiology researchers (Gulshan *et al.*, 2016)(Esteva *et al.*, 2017). Typically, CNNs are used for processing data with high-grid patterns such as images and are inspired by the organization of the animal visual cortex (Hubel and Wiesel, 1968; Fukushima, 1980). CNNs process raw data without the need for a feature-extraction stage or preprocessing. The convolution filters in a CNN are used to extract information from images such that earlier layers detect edges and

subsequent layers detect parts and complete objects such as faces or other complex geometrical shapes (Lecun *et al.*, 2015). The CNN architecture comprises three main types of layers: convolution, pooling, and fully connected layer.

One of the fundamental blocks of the convolution neural network is the convolution layer which consists of learnable filters called kernels. These filters perform convolution on the input volume and compute the dot product between the entries of the filter and the input at any position followed by nonlinear activation which results in outputs known as feature maps (Bezdan & Bačanin Džakula, 2019). Through convolution operations, CNNs can learn important features from the input images, such as edges and blobs that add up to make up the complete object in subsequent layers.

The pooling layer is used to reduce the dimensionality of feature maps by combining a set of values into a smaller number of values through means of dimensionality reduction in the feature map. The pooling operation reduces the dimensionality of the feature maps by discarding irrelevant information thus reducing the computational complexity of subsequent layers (Gholamalinezhad & Khosravi, 2020). Following several convolution and pooling layers is the fully connected layer which constitutes the final layer of the network architecture. The fully connected layer combines all the features of the previous layers across the image to identify patterns to classify the image as one of the classes as the case may be. The output size (number of nodes) of the final layer is the exact number of classes in the target class.

The input x of each layer of a CNN architecture comprises three dimensions: height, width, and depth ($h \times w \times d$) where h is equal to w . The convolution filters (kernels) in the convolution layer are also of three dimensions ($m \times m \times q$), where m must be smaller than h and q equal to or smaller than d . Similar parameters are shared through the

kernels as the basis of the local connection which each generating feature maps of size $(h - m - 1)$ (Alzubaidi *et al.*, 2021). The overall structure of a typical CNN architecture for image classification illustrated in Fig.1

Fig. 1: Typical CNN architecture (Alzubaidi *et al.*, 2021)

Applications of Artificial Intelligence to Skin Cancer Diagnosis

Five characteristics are typically used to distinguish malignant from non-malignant lesions in the clinical diagnosis of skin cancer. They are asymmetry, border irregularity, color variability, diameter greater than 6 mm, and evolution, which is referred to as the ABCDE rule (B *et al.*, 2022). CNNs are widely adopted in clinical diagnosis because of their ability to detect complex structures in images (Pathirana, 2017; Ottom, 2019; Fu'adah *et al.*, 2020; Kwiatkowska *et al.*, 2021; Medhat *et al.*, 2022; Kaur *et al.*, 2022). Several studies have been conducted on SCC diagnosis using CNNs. (A. A. Ali & Al-Marzouqi, 2017) proposed a CNN architecture comprising 17 layers including fully connected and dropout layers. The network had convolution layers, four ReLU layers, three max-pooling layers, and four dropout layers. The International Symposium on Biomedical Images (ISBI) dataset was used and the image were provided by the International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC) for training and testing. This model achieved a specificity of 0.98. (Fu'adah *et al.*, 2020) proposed a network architecture of three hidden layers with output channels of 16, 32, and 64 for each layer. The

network used optimizers such as SGD, RMSprop, Adam, and Nadam, with a learning rate of 0.001. Adam optimizer provided the best result with an accuracy of 0.99 in the classification on the ISIC dataset which comprises four classes. (Jojoa Acosta *et al.*, 2021) proposed an automated classification method for melanoma diagnosis using Mask R-CNN for image segmentation in the first stage and ResNet-152 for classification in the second stage. The model was trained on the ISIC dataset containing 1995 training, 149 validation, and 598 testing images. The model achieved an accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of 0.90, 0.82, and 0.92 respectively. (Kwiatkowska *et al.*, 2021) trained four CNNs architectures on the HAM10000 dataset containing seven different classes of skin cancer lesion types using ResNet-101, ResNeXt, SE-ResNet, and SE-ResNeXt architectures. The study used precision, sensitivity, F1-score, specificity, and Area Under the Receiver Operating Curve to validate the comparison. ResNeXt performed best with an F1-score, specificity, precision, sensitivity, and AUC of 0.74, 0.97, 0.77, 0.72, and 0.95 respectively. (Rekha *et al.*, 2021) proposed an automatic skin cancer diagnosis model that starts with feature extraction to reduce the computational complexity of the CNN architecture. The ResNet-50 architecture was used to classify images from the ISBI 2016 dataset as either melanoma or benign. The proposed model achieved an accuracy of 0.8. (Medhat *et al.*, 2022) performed a binary classification of melanoma and naevus on smartphone images using AlexNet, MobileNet-V2, and ResNet-50. The models were applied to the PAD-UFES-20 smartphone images dataset. Experimental results showed that AlexNet with Transfer Learning (TL) and data augmentation obtained accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, and F1-score of 0.99, 0.96, 0.99, 0.99, and 0.97 respectively. MobileNet -V2 with TL on the augmented dataset achieved accuracy, sensitivity,

specificity, precision, and F1-score of 0.94, 0.84, and 0.96 respectively. Finally, Resnet-50 with transfer learning and data augmentation obtained an accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, and F1-score of 0.94, 0.77, 0.98, 0.95, and 0.84 respectively.

Methodology

A systematic review highlighting the trends in computer-aided diagnostic models for melanoma diagnosis using Convolutional Neural Networks was conducted. The search strategy for this article leveraged key scientific search engines including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, Cochrane Library, Semantic Scholar, Research Gate, Science.gov, Directory of Open Access Journal, Science Direct, arXiv, IEEE Xplore, CiteSeerX, and Microsoft Academic Search. Conducted in July 2025 with a review of articles published from 1968 to 2025, a total of 332 articles were searched and reviewed in which articles that did not meet the inclusion criteria were excluded. Only 51 articles pertaining to Artificial Intelligence, Squamous Cell Carcinoma skin cancer, Convolutional Neural Networks, clinical diagnosis of skin cancer, and articles written in English were included. A systematic search was also performed to ascertain the prevalence of SCC in Africa and the level of adoption of AI for skin cancer diagnosis within the continent. The following primary keywords were used: Skin Cancer, Squamous Cell Carcinoma, and Convolutional Neural Networks.

Discussion

Comprehensive review in this study reveals a high prevalence of SCC in Africa with relatively fewer cases reported within the continent as compared to Europe; however, due to the relatively substandard healthcare system in Africa, affected persons within the continent are more likely to die from this deadly disease. There are major key barriers to widespread adoption of this indispensable technology in Africa including the willingness of technology

adoption, availability of local benchmark SCC datasets, funding and expertise in the field. Computer-driven skin cancer diagnostic techniques most especially CNNs have shown tremendous performance in skin cancer diagnosis – significantly outperforming traditional clinical diagnostic techniques. Finally, this study recommends training researchers in Africa in the field of Deep Learning for SCC diagnosis, and the creation of benchmark SCC datasets for training and model testing.

Conclusion

Among various skin cancers, SCC is considered one of the deadliest, accounting for approximately 75% of deaths from related diseases worldwide. Although SCC is deadly, timely and accurate diagnosis can significantly facilitate the survival of affected individuals. The prevalence of SCC in Africa is relatively low with fewer cases reported within the continent; however, due to the relatively substandard healthcare system in Africa compared to Europe and other continents, affected persons in Africa are more likely to die from this deadly disease. This study revealed some of the current barriers to widespread adoption of AI for diagnosis in Africa including general awareness of the technology, lack of trained personnel in the field, unwillingness to adopt the technology, and funding. AI skin cancer diagnostic techniques particularly CNNs have shown tremendous performance in skin cancer diagnosis significantly outperforming traditional clinical diagnostic techniques. Therefore, there is an increasing demand for the widespread adoption of AI techniques for SCC diagnosis in Africa to significantly reduce the mortality rate of SCC patients.

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